

BUCKLING BEHAVIOUR OF UNSYMMETRIC ANGLE-PLY RECTANGULAR PLATES

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BUCKLING OF UNSYMMETRIC ANGLE-PLY PLATE WITH VARIOUS EDGD CONDITIONS

Consider an unsymmetric angle-ply rectangular plate under uniform compressive in the x-direction as shown in Figure 1. The differential equations governing the buckling behavior of the plate can be expressed as

$$L_i(\delta u, \delta v, \delta w) = 0 \quad (i=1,2,3) \quad (1)$$

We chose to solve the problem that the plate is simple supported edge along the loaded edges and arbitrary boundary conditions along the other edges. The variations of buckling deformations are assumed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta u &= \sum_{i=0}^N a_i \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} u_i(y) & \delta v &= \sum_{i=0}^N b_i \cos \frac{m\pi x}{a} v_i(y) \\ \delta w &= \sum_{i=0}^N c_i \sin \frac{m\pi x}{a} w_i(y) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

in which $u_i(y)$, $v_i(y)$ and $w_i(y)$ are liner combinations of equidistant point quintic B spline function $\phi_s(y/h-i)$.

Substituting the expression (2) into equations (1) yields internal residual

$$R_{Ii} = \bar{L}_i [(\{u_j(y)\})^T, (\{v_j(y)\})^T, (\{w_j(y)\})^T] \cdot (\{a_j\}, \{b_j\}, \{c_j\}) \cdot S_j(x) \quad (3)$$

$(i = 1, 2, 3)$

Selecting the weighted function as follow

$$W_{Ii} = h_i(x) \delta(y-y_j) \quad i=1,2,3 \quad j=0,1,2, \dots, N \quad (4)$$

then

$$\int_0^a \int_0^b R_{Ii} W_{Ii} dx dy = 0 \quad (5)$$

After a series of complicated calculations, we obtain the following standard eigenvalue equation by Caussion elimination method.

$$|A - \lambda I|_{n \times n} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Solving the equation (6), the buckling load is obtained.

ANALYSES AND DISCUSSIONS

Numerical calculations were made for unsymmetric angle-ply square plates; the materials considered are graphite/epoxy. The Young's modulus, shear modulus and Poisson's ratio for that are, respectively $E1/E2=40$, $G12/E2=0.5$, $\nu12=0.25$. For convenience to illus-

trate, we only list the results of the calculations and analyses of three type boundary condition laminates.

- (1) Simply supported boundary condition along four edges (denoted by A).
- (2) Simply supported boundary conditions along the loaded edges, clamped supportde along the other edges (denoted by B).
- (3) Simply supported along the loaded edges, the other edges one is simply supported, one clamped (denoted by C).

Figure 2 illustrates the effect of ply angles upon the buckling load $K = \bar{N}c^2/E_2t^3$ of unsymmetric four layer square plates in different edge boundary conditions. The buckling load is a function of ply angles. As the ply angles increase to a proper value, the buckling load attains a maximum. Its value is 57.67% larger than that of at $\theta=0$. But the coupling stiffnesses increase in the region $0 < \theta < 45^\circ$ as shown in Figure 3, the coupling stiffnesses are the factors of decreasing the buckling load. Studying the reason of generating the phenomenon is very useful and interesting.

The buckling load of four layer equal ply thickness simply supported laminated plate is expressed as

$$\bar{N}_x = \left(\frac{a}{m\pi}\right)^2 (T_{33} + \frac{2T_{12}T_{23}T_{13} - T_{22}T_{13}^2 - T_{11}T_{23}^2}{T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2}) \quad K = \bar{N}_x b^2/E_2t^3 \quad K = K_1 + K_2$$

$$K_1 = \left(\frac{ab}{m\pi}\right)^2 \frac{T_{33}}{E_2t^3} \quad K_2 = \left(\frac{ab}{m\pi}\right)^2 \frac{2T_{12}T_{23}T_{13} - T_{22}T_{13}^2 - T_{11}T_{23}^2}{E_2t^3 (T_{11}T_{22} - T_{12}^2)} \quad (7)$$

Figure 4 illustrates the effect of ply angles upon K , K_1 and K_2 . The variety of K_1 is the most significant in this Figure, it is the main factor which has influence on K . The variety of K_1 is less, and K_2 is negative value (influenced by the coupling effect) and has negative influence on K . The K and K_1 attain absolute maximums at $\theta=45^\circ$ in the same time.

$$K_1 = K_{s1} + K_{s2}$$

$$K_{s1} = \left(\frac{ab}{m\pi}\right)^2 \frac{1}{E_2t^3} [D_{11}\left(\frac{m\pi}{a}\right)^4 + D_{22}\left(\frac{n\pi}{b}\right)^4] \quad (8)$$

$$K_{s2} = \left(\frac{ab}{m\pi}\right)^2 \frac{1}{E_2t^3} [2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})\left(\frac{m\pi}{a}\right)^2 \left(\frac{n\pi}{b}\right)^2]$$

Figure 5 illustrates the effect of ply angles upon K_1 , K_{s1} . When ply angles vary the variation of the value of K_{s1} is small. But its slope suddenly varies which leads to K_1 's slope change. The change of K_{s2} value is the largest in this Figure. The K_1 and K_{s2} attain absolute maximums at $\theta=45^\circ$. We have come to the conclusion that D_{12} and D_{66} are the key factors increasing the buckling load.

The bending stiffnesses D_{12} and D_{66} are ascending in the region $0 < \theta < 45^\circ$ as shown in Figure 6. The reason that D_{12} and D_{66} increase with ply angle is the effect of stiffnesses coefficients \bar{Q}_{12} and \bar{Q}_{66} on that, which are monotonic ascension in this region and attain absolute maximums at $\theta=45^\circ$.

Figure 7 illustrates the effect of ply thickness t_1 upon the buckling load of unsymmetric four layer simply supported laminated square plate. Selecting the proper ply thicknesses can make the buckling load increases. The reason that the variations of ply thicknesses lead to the coupling stiffnesses decreasing rapidly. When the ply thickness varies to a certain fixed value, the coupling stiffnesses will vanish. The strict theoretical proof is omitted from this paper.

The buckling load of unsymmetric four-layer simply supported edges laminated plates by selecting proper ply thicknesses compared with that of equal ply thicknesses in shown as Figure 8.

The numerical results of the maximum values of the buckling load in the three boundary conditions is shown in table 1.

CONCLUSION

(1). The boundary effect seriously influences upon the value of the buckling load. The buckling load in B type boundary condition is the largest in the three boundary conditions. The buckling load is 58% larger than that of in A type boundary condition. So to change the supported conditions is a important way to increase the critical load.

(2) Selecting proper ply thickness, the coupling stiffnesses vanish and the buckling load will increase.

(3) The main reason that the buckling load increases with ply angles increase is the effect of \bar{Q}_{12} and \bar{Q}_{66} . In the region $0 < \theta < 45^\circ$, the stiffness coefficients \bar{Q}_{12} and \bar{Q}_{66} are monotonic increasing, so \bar{Q}_{12} and \bar{Q}_{66} are very important factors to increase the buckling load.

Table 1. Maximum value of the buckling loads in the three boundary conditions for unsymmetric laminated square plates

$$K = \bar{N} x b^2 / E_2 t^3 \quad a/b=1 \quad \text{number of half-wave } m=1$$

LN	BC	ply angle (degree)						ply thickness (mm)			K'	K''	K''/K'
		θ_1	θ_2	θ_3	θ_4	θ_5	θ_6	t1	t2	t3			
IV	A	45.00	45.00	45.00	45.00			.1486	.3594		35.838	67.623	1.89
	B	40.58	40.58	40.58	40.58			.1490	.3590		39.914	107.73	1.67
	C	47.65	47.65	47.65	47.65			.1488	.3592		37.378	89.994	1.41
VI	A	44.97	44.97	44.97	44.97	44.97	44.97	.1413	.3082	.1325	35.838	67.618	1.89
	B	41.44	41.44	41.44	41.44	41.44	41.44	.1415	.3126	.3079	39.914	108.93	1.73
	C	47.95	47.95	47.95	47.95	47.95	47.95	.1424	.3100	.3096	37.378	90.207	1.41

In this table K' is the buckling load when ply angles are equal to zero and equal thickness layers; K'' is the absolute maximum value of the buckling load. LN is the number of the layer; BC is the boundary condition.

Fig.1 Laminated plates with orthotropic layers.

Fig. 2 K versus θ .

Fig.3. B_{ij} versus θ .

Fig.4 Effect of θ on K, K_1 , and K_2 .

Fig.5 Effect of θ on K_1, K_{s1} and K_{s2} .

Fig.6 D_{ij} versus θ .

Fig.7 Relation between K and t_1 .

Fig.8 Relation between K and θ .